

The Endeavours of the Democratic Government to achieve the Nationwide Ceasefire Agreement (2010-2015)

Kyaw Wana Aung*

Abstract

The nationwide ceasefire agreement (NCA) seeks to achieve a negotiated settlement between the government of Myanmar and non-state ethnic armed organizations (EAOs) that paves the way for peace-building and national dialogue. There are several non-state ethnic armed organizations until 2010. They are divided into two groups: the National Ceasefire Coordination Team (NCCT) members and Non-NCCT members. The Arakan Liberation Party (ALP), Chin National Front (CNF), Democratic Karen Benevolent Army (DKBA), KNU/KNLA-Peace Council (KNU/KNLA-PC), Karenni National Progressive Party (KNPP), Karen National Union (KNU), New Mon State Party (NMSP), Pa-O National Liberation Party (PNLO), Shan State Progress Party/Shan State Army-North (SSPP/SSA-N), Kachin Independence Organization (KIO), Arakan Army (AA), Myanmar National Democracy Alliance Army (MNDAA), Ta'ang National Liberation Army (TNLA), Arakan National Council (ANC), Lahu Democratic Union (LDU), and Wa National Organization Army (WNO) are included in the NCCT. The Non-NCCT members are All Burma Students' Democratic Front (ABSDF), National Democratic Alliance Army-Eastern Shan State (NDAA), National Socialist Council of Nagaland-Khaplang (NSCN-K), Restoration Council of Shan State/Shan State Army-South (RCSS/SSA-S), and United Wa State Army/Party (UWSA). Most of the NCCT members except AA, MNDAA, TNLA, ANC, LDU, and WNO and all the members of the Non-NCCT were invited by the government to sign the NCA, but KIO rejected to sign the NCA.

Keywords : Negotiation Structure and Actors, Text of the NCA, Short-term Implementation, UNFC-UPWC Talks, NCCT-UPWC Talk Process, Challenge of Federalism, and Other Major Challenges

Introduction

Negotiation Structure and Actors

Union-level negotiations had been conducted through a tripartite structure of government, ethnic, and third-party representatives. In this structure, the government, the Hluttaw (Parliament), and the Tatmadaw (Myanmar Army) had been represented through the dual Union Peace-making Committees. These consisted of an 11-member "Central Committee" (UPCC) chaired by President U Thein Sein, and a 52-member "Working Committee" (UPWC) running the actual negotiations, headed by Vice-president Sai Mauk Kham and composed of largely regional-level representatives. U Aung Min was one of four vice-chairmen of the UPWC and also the government's chief negotiator.

Around 21 EAOs had been in some way engaged in the NCA process. Four of these groups—the United Wa State Army (UWSA), National Democratic Alliance Army (NDAA), National Socialist Council of Nagaland-Khaplang (NSCN-K), and the Restoration Council of Shan State (RCSS/SSA-S)—were invited by the UPWC to participate in negotiations bilaterally, and although the RCSS/SSA-S had attended NCA meetings with the UNFC, these EAOs had chosen not to participate yet in the NCA negotiations.

The remaining organizations had either directly or indirectly participated in negotiations through membership in or close affiliation to either the 13-member United Nationalities Federal Council (UNFC), and in or the loosely UNFC-based 16-member National Ceasefire Coordination Team (NCCT).

* Lecturer, Department of History, Dagon University

The UNFC represents 13 ethnic armed groups including: Kachin Independence Organization (KIO), New Mon State Party (NMSP), Shan State Progress Party/Shan State Army-North (SSPP/SSA-N), Karen National Union (KNU), Karenni National Progressive Party (KNPP), Chin National Front (CNF), Lahu Democratic Union (LDU), Arakan National Council (ANC), Pa-O National Liberation Organization (PNLO), Ta'ang National Liberation Army (TNLA), Wa National Organization/Army (WNO), MNDAA. The KNU suspended membership in September 2014.

The NCCT represents 16 ethnic armed groups including: Arakan Army (AA), Arakan Liberation Party (ALP), Arakan National Council (ANC), Chin National Front (CNF), Democratic Karen Benevolent Army (DKBA), Kachin Independence Organization (KIO), Karenni National Progressive Party (KNPP), Karen National Union/Karen National Liberation Army-Peace Council (KNU/KNLA-PC), Lahu Democratic Union (LDU), Myanmar National Democracy Alliance Army (MNDAA), New Mon State Party (NMSP), Pa-O National Liberation Organization (PNLO), Shan State Progress Party/Shan State Army-North (SSPP/SSA-N), Ta'ang National Liberation Army (TNLA), and Wa National Organization/Army (WNO). Over the course of negotiations the NCCT had effectively grown into the most prominent representative of EAO interests throughout the NCA negotiation process.

The overall peace process itself was coordinated by the multi-purpose Myanmar Peace Center (MPC) - a quasi-governmental body headed by Minister of the President's Office U Aung Min and run by various government and civil society representatives. The MPC was designed as a secretariat to support the chief negotiator and the UPWC as well as reporting to the President's Office. It also facilitated some third-party involvement in the peace process and provided third-parties with a platform through which they could engage.

UNFC-UPWC Talks

A. The First Chiangmai Meeting

President U Thein Sein government made overture for peace talks, with the indication of taking steps from ceasefire to political dialogue on August 18, 2011. The UPWC met only with individual organizations and, in the years 2011-2012, entered into ceasefire agreements with individual organizations, designated as state-level and union-level agreements. Those bilateral agreements with the EAOs, which were not in the process of fighting as well as those which were in the process of fighting. However, clashes continued to occur even though the ceasefire agreements had been signed.

After 2012, the UPWC started to come and meet with UNFC informally. In February 2013, the UNFC and UPWC started to hold, in Chiangmai, preliminary political discussions on framework for political dialogue.

B. The Second Chiangmai Meeting

The second meeting on framework for political dialogue was held in September, 2013 again in Chiangmai, Thailand. In the second meeting, representatives of the Non-UNFC members were invited to attend the meeting, on the principle of UNFC+. In the arrangement, the ALP was invited as joint delegation member of the UNFC and representatives of the All-Burma Students' Democratic Federation (ABSDF) was invited as observers. In addition, broad-based political parties inside the country, the two main ethnic alliance parties, which were the 1990 election-winning political party alliance, being the United Nationalities Alliance (UNA), and the 2010 election-winning political party alliance, being the National Brotherhood Federation (NBF)-two representatives from each of the alliance were invited to attend the meetings as observers.

In order to be of assistance in future political dialogue process, Daw Aung San Suu Kyi was also invited, as a leader of the democratic movement of Burma (now the State Counsellor), to attend the meetings as an observer. However, Daw Aung San Suu Kyi and representatives from the NBF were not able to attend the meetings.

At the second preliminary political dialogue meeting, the UPWC demanded again the signing of ceasefire agreement, in advance. The UNFC, according to its stand, made the counter proposal of signing the ceasefire agreement only at the stage when the talks were to advance to the political

dialogue, as the majority of the ethnic organizations had signed the ceasefire agreements, at the state as well as at the union-level.

The question had to be raised as to what kind of ceasefire agreement had to be signed by the ethnic organizations, which had signed the agreement at the state and union levels. Answer from the UPWC side was to reaffirm the agreements, signed at the state and union levels, and to add two more terms. The two more terms were:

1. to draft Framework for Political Dialogue; and
2. to hold political conference.

As the consultations did not progress well, the UPWC side ended the consultation process by saying that it had come to meet, in accordance with its promise made at the first time, and to receive just the UNFC proposed framework.

NCCT-UPWC Talk Process

A. Laiza Conference

The EAROs continued to find means and ways for gathering and holding a conference at the KIO Headquarters in Laiza, from the end of October to the beginning of November 2013. Subsequently, the Laiza Agreement was formulated for approaching the various steps of political dialogue process, after reaching the ceasefire agreement demanded by President U Thein Sein government. In order to implement that agreement, the Nationwide Ceasefire Coordination Team (NCCT) had to be formed. On the basis of equality among the ethnic nationalities, the NCCT was formed with 16 members, one representative from each of the 16 organizations.

B. Myitkyina Conference

Based on the Laiza Agreement, launched on November 4, 2013 in Myitkyina, Kachin State, the NCCT was able to hold talks with the UPWC. At the first NCCT-UPWC Myitkyina talk, the military representatives produced an agreement prepared by them in advance, as a secret card, and proposed for it. That draft was a combination of some of the terms, acceptable to them, from the Framework for Political Dialogue prepared by the EAROs, and the terms desired by them. As the NCCT had to transform the 11-point Liza Agreement into the form of a pact, the Myitkyina meeting was ended with an agreement to hold a consultation meeting once more, in the future.

C. Lawkheela Conference

Subsequently, from January 20 to 25, 2014, the first Lawkheela Conference of the EAROs was held in the KNU administered area and the NCCT's draft counter proposal, in the form of a pact, was formulated and adopted. The draft pact was a preparation made by combining terms taken out from the framework for the political dialogue, which had been formulated to be a certain extent, and terms relating to military matters.

D. Chiangmai Meeting

The group led by U Aung Min from the UPWC came to Chiangmai on January 29, 2014 and officially accepted that draft. Later, as there was a complaint that the text of pact was inflated and too thick, and a proposal was made for transforming the draft into a compact form, a consultation meeting had to be held again.

In the continuation of the consultations, stands of the two sides became hardened increasingly in regard of "Their Version, Our Version," and as the livelihood of deadlock was foreseen, the two sides strived on after laying down the position of having only one version. In this way the idea of a "Single Text" emerged and the two sides continued to march on. As the UPWC accepted the idea, The NCA Single Text draft emerged.

Text of the NCA

The Text of the NCA consisted of 7 chapters and 33 paragraphs which detail the NCA's (1) basic principles, (2) aims and objectives, (3) ceasefire premises, (4) guidelines and regulations

governing the ceasefire, (5) guarantees for political dialogue, (6) future tasks and responsibilities, and (7) administrative obligations and guidelines for dispute settlement. In terms of inclusivity, the NCA stated the aim to include all “relevant” EAOs in the signing of the NCA.

In the Chapter I, the accord is signed in its currently published form, signatories agree to the basic principle of establishing a federal union “ in the split of Panglong, while upholding the principles of “ non-disintegration of the Union and perpetuation of national sovereignty.” These principles will be implemented “in accordance with the outcomes of a future political dialogue.”

The Chapter II provides the outlines of the intention of the signatory parties to begin a process of inclusive political dialogue.

In the Chapter III, the agreements specifies activities that will not be allowed including: violence-inciting propaganda, armed conflict, troop reinforcement and recruitment, the establishment of new military bases, and the laying of landmines, all unless specifically agreed to by the parties to the conflict. Chapter III also expands upon these provisions by highlighting the guidelines for the deployment of military forces, demarcation of areas of control, communications between the parties, movement of troops, the protection of civilians, and provision of humanitarian assistance. It also provides for joint work on landmine clearance and in the administration of rule of law in ceasefire areas.

Chapter IV of the text lays out the roles and responsibilities of the joint implementation committee, which will reach decisions by consensus. It also states that the Military Code of Conduct and other rules and regulations applicable to the NCA will be enacted within a month of the signing.

In the Chapter V, a roadmap is outlined according to the political dialogue which is to take place as well as planning for security reintegration within 90 days after the NCA signed. Chapter V of the agreement gives guarantees for the political dialogue which is of utmost importance for the EAOs as no ceasefire in Myanmar in the past has moved to a political dialogue phase.

Chapter VI lays out further tasks and responsibilities including confidence-building measures such as removal of signatory EAORs from listing under the Unlawful Association Act, and the release of person detained under this Act. Also of none in this chapter is that EAORs will be allowed to implement “interim arrangements” which include: health, education, and socio-economic service delivery, as well as environmental conservation, drug eradication, cultural promotion, international and national aid and private sector activities.

Chapter VII contains miscellaneous points on overall implementation of the NCA.

The Second Lawkheela Conference

Though the NCCT-UPWC held official talks for up to seventh times, in a period of over one year, the NCA could not be concluded. Accordingly, Lawkheela summit conference had to be held again, in June 2015, and laid down the positions of continuing the endeavor with the Senior Delegation (SD) and to sign the NCA, only when all the members were allowed to sign it. The composition of SD was only 17 members. They are:

1. Kachin Independence Organization (KIO)
2. Karen National Union (KNU)
3. Karenni National Progressive Party (KNPP)
4. New Mon State Party (NMSP)
5. Shan State Progress Party (SSPP)
6. Chin National Front (CNF)
7. Pa-O National Liberation Organization (PNLO)
8. Palaung State Liberation Front (PSLF)
9. Democratic Karen Benevolent Army (DKBA)

Short-term Implementation

According to the Chapter 4 of the Text of NCA thirty days after the agreement the next timetable was to be laid out. At that point a Joint Monitoring Committee (JMC) and the Union Peace Dialogue Joint Committee (UPDJC) must also be put together to carry the peace process forward. Chapter 5 of the Text of NCA dictated that ninety days after the agreement the UPDJC must have drawn up a framework for political dialogue and began to move towards its implementation. Finally within 90 days after the agreement political dialogue could begin, including discussions around security reintegration.

Six principles of Tatmadaw

The Tatmadaw adopted “six principles” to serve as its guideline and position towards the ceasefire process. The “Six Principles” are as follows:

1. To have a keen desire to reach eternal peace
2. To keep promises agreed to in peace deals
3. To avoid capitalizing on the peace agreement
4. To avoid placing a heavy burden on local people
5. To strictly abide by the existing laws
6. To “March” towards a democratic country in accordance to the 2008 Constitution

Non-Conveniences between Tatmadaw and EAROs

There were also concerns that the task must not be accomplished before the 2015 election. There had been a number of instances where government officials and ethnic leaders had declared that the NCA was within reach, only to see complications and postponements. The Tatmadaw’s demanded that ethnic groups disarm, demobilize and reintegrate, along with its manoeuvres in ceasefire areas are sources of continued mistrust and disagreement. Continuing fighting, ceasefire violations and actions by parties benefiting from conflict risk reversing the gains.

The NCA would be the first major step of many more to come, and must well be the easiest. The agreement would stipulate commencing political dialogue within 90 days of signing, and this dialogue promises to be more tedious and prolonged than the NCA negotiations. Fundamental issues such as the structure of the state, the Tatmadaw and the EAROs’ roles, socio-economic integration, revenue sharing and constitutional amendments would have to be discussed.

The ongoing NCA negotiations only involved the Government, Military and EAROs, while the political dialogue would see a diversification of stakeholders as political parties, civil society and women’s groups became involved. That would enable the negotiations to be more comprehensive, but also likely to be drawn-out.

The Challenge of Federalism

One of the major hurdles would definitely be on federalism. The government’s agreement to a federal system was a major breakthrough. Successive governments and the Tatmadaw had regarded federalism as anathema and a precursor to Balkanization, while ethnic groups and pro-democracy activists considered federalism as the only suitable of government for Myanmar. That said, different groups had different interpretations and expectations of federalism, meaning it would have to be negotiated at length.

In addition, the current notion of federalism espoused by its proponents was based on ethnicity, where power would be devolved based on ethnic groups and their geographic distribution. While Myanmar had administrative units based on major ethnic groups, they were not homogenous and had various other self-identifying ethnic groups residing within.

The EAROs had also linked federalism with the need for a federal army, but there was confusion on what it actually should be whether a unified military that accepted all citizens regardless of ethnicity or each administrative unit entitled to a military formed along ethnic lines.

Other Major Challenges

10. Karen National Union-Peace Council (KNU-PC)
11. Arakan Liberation Party (ALP)
12. Arakan National Council (ANC)
13. Arakan Army (AA)
14. Lahu Democratic Union (LDU)
15. Wa National Organization (WNO)
16. Myanmar National Democratic Alliance Army (MNDAA)
17. All-Burma Students' Democratic Front (ABSDF)

SD-UPWC Talk

SD-UPWC meeting had to be held two times and the 9th meeting for talks on NCA was held and the NCA draft had to be concluded in an immature form, on August 7, 2015. The NCA consisted of 33 Articles. Article 33 concerned the section on the signatories, but it was left out as an exception, as if it had nothing to do with the agreement, and the government adopted it in a rush. In the section on signatories, the government did not accept the 6 organizations mentioned below.

1. Arakan National; Council (ANC)
2. Arakan Army (AA)
3. Lahu Democratic Union (LDU)
4. Wa National Organization (WNO)
5. Myanmar National Democratic Alliance Army (MNDAA)
6. Palaung State Liberation Front (PSLF)

The Meetings of Top Leaders of the EAROs

The EARO's stand was that the NCA became adopted only when all the articles in the NCA were agreed upon. In July and August of 2015, the meeting of top leaders of EAROs was called and decision was made to meet directly with the President and Chief of the Defence Services (Commander-in-Chief of the Armed Forces) and find the means and ways for having all-inclusiveness. The means and ways were, giving full guarantees relating to military, political and social matters, to those, who were not allowed to sign the NCA.

SD Leaders and the Government (Naypyidaw)

Three SD leaders together with the five top leaders of EAROs went to Naypyidaw on September 9, 2015 for consultation. However, they had no opportunity to meet with Chief of the Defence Services. They had the opportunity to meet with the President and they received no clear-cut answer with regard to the guarantees they asked for the 6 NCCT members, whom the government had not recognized.

The Second Meeting of Top Leaders of EAROs

The meeting of top leaders of EAROs was held again in September 2015, and position with regard to signing or not signing the NCA was considered and adopted. The UNFC decided to continue holding the principle of all-inclusiveness, adopted by the Laiza and Lawkheela conferences and meetings of the top leaders. However, organizations desiring to sign the NCA deviated from decisions for all-inclusiveness laid down by the Laiza and Lawkheela conferences, and made the resolution of signing the NCA, according to the decision of each individual organization. Hence the result was an NCA signed between the 8 EAROs and the government on November 8, 2015. The groups which signed were RCSS/SSA-S, KNU, CNF, ALP, PNLO, KNU/KNLA-PC, DKBA, and ABSDF.

The other major challenge was that the entire negotiation process remains heavily personalized, spearheaded by individuals such as President Thein Sein and ethnic leaders. The personalization means that all parties were dealing with uncertainty on how their counterparts, successors and subordinates would approach issues, and a bad apple could quickly derail the entire process. Institutional mechanisms were being cultivated but remain unable to supplant the heavily personalized form of political participation endemic to Myanmar.

Other issues that would require attention include refugees and internally displaced persons, landmines, the Border Guard and People's Militia Forces (former EAROs and factions aligned to and supported by the Tatmadaw), transnational crime, illegal immigration, drug production and environmental destruction. These would have to be dealt with in conjunction with national-level political and economic liberalization, growing religious sectarianism and constitutional reform. There was also uncertainty surrounding the Wa, the largest and best-equipped Ethnic Armed Group (EAG) with its own de facto state, and a number of EAROs whom the government did not consider eligible to participate in the NCA.

Conclusion

The Nationwide Ceasefire Agreement (NCA) was signed between the 8 EAROs and the government headed by President U Thein Sein on November 8, 2015. It was not also in accordance with Article (2-D) of the NCA, requiring the signing by all, in concert, and the essence of NCA had become spoiled. So long as all-inclusiveness was not realized, the Framework for Political Dialogue and the so-called Union Peace Conference, emanating from it would still be lacking any essence.

While the ceasefire negotiations were underway, fighting continued between the Tatmadaw and several of the ethnic organizations' militias. Among the UNFC members, the Tatmadaw engaged in frequent skirmishes with AA, the MNDA, the SSPP, and the TNLA in Shan State, and with less frequency with the Kachin Independence Army (KIA) in Kachin State. The Tatmadaw also periodically exchanged fire with the NSCN-K and the UWSA. The Tatmadaw reportedly attacked SSPP forces on October 7, after the group announced it would not sign the ceasefire agreement. The Tatmadaw had previously stated it would not attack groups who did not sign the ceasefire agreements.

Launching military offensives on the one hand and holding peace talks on the other was not the way to bring genuine, just and honorable peace. Under these circumstances, just as the democracy could not flourish, a genuine federal union could not be established.

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ကျမ်းကိုးစာရင်း

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